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Motion Trajectory Prediction in Dynamic Human-Robot Shared Workspaces

Samuele Dell’Oca^{*1}, Vincenzo Cutrona¹, Elias Montini^{1,2}, Davide Matteri¹, Sara Masiero¹,
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Abstract—Human motion trajectory prediction plays a critical role in enabling safe and efficient Human-Robot Collaboration, particularly in industrial workplaces where robots and workers share space and operate in close proximity. Here, the ability to forecast future human positions enables proactive adaptation, improved path planning, and enhanced safety. This work builds on an extensive analysis of state-of-the-art motion prediction approaches and presents a training-less prototype that predicts human motion in indoor workspaces. The system is validated in both static and dynamic scenarios: first with fixed cameras in a controlled setting, then onboard an Autonomous Mobile Robot navigating a shared workspace. Validation results show reliable short-term predictions, while performance declines over longer time horizons and in multi-worker scenarios due to occlusions, perspective changes, and lack of identity tracking. Despite these limitations, the approach provides a solid foundation for future enhancements, including the integration of contextual awareness and more robust prediction models, to support reactive planning and ensure real-time safety in dynamic and complex industrial environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial workplaces are evolving rapidly with the increasing adoption of automation, collaborative robots (cobots), and Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs). Especially when bringing these technologies to shared environments, i.e., environments where humans and robots co-exist, a seamless workplace transformation necessitates intelligent systems capable of understanding human behavior and adapt to it, ensuring safety, efficiency, and smooth coordination [1]. Human motion trajectory prediction is of particular importance to proactively adjust robotic systems to human behavior, by sensing, predicting and finally anticipating human movements. An accurate motion prediction reduces the risk of collisions, while enhancing Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC), productivity and adaptability within industrial settings [2]. However, achieving high accuracy in motion trajectory prediction requires the integration and optimization of various technologies, including pose recognition, position tracking, orientation detection, and predictive modeling. Additional challenges lie in the inherent complexity, variability, and intention-driven nature of human movement [3].

Although the problem is widely studied in different literature domains, spanning various contexts such as pedestrian

monitoring in urban traffic, construction sites and indoor environments [4], current research does not adequately address the specific constraints of industrial environments, e.g., robot proximity, rapid task changes, and structured yet dynamic conditions [5]. As a result, datasets available in literature often fail to account for human behavior in the presence of robots, leading to data distributions that diverge from real-world scenarios.

By combining existing Computer Vision (CV) methods with prediction models, this research investigates the prediction of human motion trajectories in shared indoor industrial environments. Emphasis is placed on dynamic constraints characteristic of industrial settings, such as sensor mobility, shifting visual fields, and evolving layouts. Additionally, the study examines the application of training-free prediction models to overcome the challenges posed by insufficient training data. To this end, a prototypal solution is proposed, implementing a two-stage human motion trajectory prediction system. In the first stage, workers’ poses are detected using state-of-the-art CV techniques. In the second stage, the extracted pose features are utilized to predict future positions through a modified Kalman Filter (KF) approach. The system is initially deployed in a static indoor workspace, allowing for baseline performance validation. Subsequently, it is adapted to operate within a human-robot shared laboratory environment, specifically mounted onboard an AMR. This dynamic deployment scenario provides an opportunity to assess the prototype’s robustness against the previously discussed real-world, industry-like constraints.

The primary contribution of this work is a comparative analysis of human motion trajectory prediction performance between fixed and dynamic configurations, highlighting the associated challenges and identifying avenues for potential improvements. Additionally, an in-depth overview of existing approaches in the literature is provided. This contextual analysis helps position the proposed investigation within the broader research landscape, emphasizing its novelty and practical relevance.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: starting from an extensive state-of-the-art analysis in Section II, the work materials and methods are formalized in Section III. Section IV details the validation of the system prototype within the two configurations and the associated results and limitations. Finally, conclusions and future improvements are discussed in Section V.

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TABLE I: Overview of existing approaches to human motion trajectory prediction in the literature

Work	Year	Model	Category	Context	Work	Year	Model	Category	Context
[6]	2016	KF	Physics-based	Construction site	[31]	2022	SFM	Physics-based	Urban evacuation
[7]	2016	LSTM	Pattern-based	Urban traffic	[32]	2022	Transf.+RNN	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[8]	2018	IRL	Planning-based	Indoor environ.	[33]	2022	Transf.+MC	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[9]	2018	LSTM	Pattern-based	Urban traffic	[34]	2023	LSTM	Pattern-based	Construction site
[10]	2018	MDP	Planning-based	Indoor environ.	[35]	2023	Custom	Planning-based	Indoor workspace
[11]	2019	MDP	Planning-based	Urban traffic	[36]	2023	CNN	Pattern-based	Robotic environ.
[12]	2019	SFM	Physics-based	Urban evacuation	[37]	2023	SFM	Physics-based	Urban traffic
[13]	2019	UKF	Physics-based	Urban traffic	[38]	2023	SFM+CUKF	Physics-based	Urban traffic
[14]	2019	IRL+LSTM	Pattern-based	Urban traffic	[39]	2023	GNN	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[15]	2020	LSTM	Pattern-based	Construction site	[40]	2023	STGCN+RL	Pattern-based	Robotic environ.
[16]	2020	LSTM	Pattern-based	Robotic environ.	[41]	2023	CVAE	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[17]	2020	LSTM	Pattern-based	Robotic environ.	[42]	2023	VAE	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[18]	2020	SFM	Physics-based	Urban evacuation	[43]	2023	Custom	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[19]	2020	SFM	Physics-based	Urban evacuation	[4]	2024	RNN+GNN	Pattern-based	Robotic environ.
[20]	2020	KF	Physics-based	Robotic environ.	[44]	2024	LSTM	Pattern-based	Construction site
[21]	2020	PKF	Physics-based	Outdoor environ.	[45]	2024	SFM	Physics-based	Urban traffic
[22]	2020	IRL	Planning-based	Urban traffic	[46]	2024	Custom	Planning-based	Indoor environ.
[23]	2020	Custom	Planning-based	Robotic environ.	[47]	2024	POMDP	Planning-based	Urban traffic
[24]	2020	CVAE	Pattern-based	Robotic environ.	[48]	2024	Custom	Planning-based	Urban traffic
[25]	2020	RNN	Pattern-based	Robotic environ.	[49]	2024	LSTM+GAT	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[26]	2021	SFM	Physics-based	Urban traffic	[50]	2024	Custom	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[27]	2021	SFM	Physics-based	Urban traffic	[51]	2024	Custom	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[28]	2021	IRL	Planning-based	Urban traffic	[52]	2024	CVAE	Pattern-based	Urban traffic
[29]	2021	Custom	Pattern-based	Urban traffic	[53]	2025	SFM	Physics-based	Urban traffic
[30]	2022	BEKF+SFM	Physics-based	Urban traffic	[54]	2025	Custom	Pattern-based	Urban traffic

II. STATE OF THE ART

The prediction of human motion trajectories has been the subject of extensive investigation across a variety of application domains. Existing modelling approaches can be broadly categorized into three main groups: physics-based, planning-based, and data-driven (pattern-based) methods [55]. These approaches differ fundamentally in how they represent human motion and the assumptions they impose. Physics-based methods employ explicit dynamical models grounded in Newton’s laws of motion. Planning-based approaches emphasize the inference of motion intent based on the behaviour of rational agents. Conversely, pattern-based methods extract and generalize motion patterns from observed trajectory data. A comprehensive summary of different applications of these methodologies is presented in Table I.

A. Physics-based Models

Physics-based models are grounded in motion equations and rely on assumptions such as constant velocity or acceleration. Notable examples include Social Force Models (SFM) and KFs, along with their widely used variants like Extended Kalman Filters (EKFs) and Unscented Kalman Filters (UKFs). These models are valued for their real-time performance and simplicity, often serving as baselines in motion prediction tasks. A key characteristic is their ability to perform fast and deterministic predictions under well-defined dynamics. However, their primary limitation lies in their reliance on linear and Gaussian motion assumptions, which do not hold in many human behaviors—especially during intention-driven actions or task transitions. As a result, physics-based models tend to underperform in capturing the variability and non-linearity of human motion in real-world environments.

Existing SFM-based solutions in the literature are primarily developed in two distinct contexts: urban pedestrian monitoring and emergency evacuations. Recent efforts have focused on enhancing SFM to better capture complex pedestrian behaviors [26]. Contextual features have been integrated to simulate high-density crowd dynamics and stopping actions [27]. Advances in bidirectional pedestrian flow simulation include modifications to better represent two-way streams [37] and the introduction of additional collision avoidance forces to enhance realism under pandemic-like conditions [45]. A fusion-based SFM has been developed to improve lane formation and movement efficiency through dynamic speed adjustment and alignment correction mechanisms [53]. In parallel, several adaptations of the SFM have been proposed for emergency evacuation modeling, addressing unique situational factors. Extensions designed for shipwreck scenarios have highlighted the influence of gravity and social interactions on crowd behavior [12]. Revisions targeting post-earthquake evacuations have incorporated dynamic environmental changes [18], while the integration of smoke propagation dynamics has been used to simulate reduced visibility conditions [19]. To further enhance realism, behavioral heterogeneity has been incorporated into the SFM framework, accounting for diverse individual responses during evacuation [31].

On the other hand, motion prediction using KF-based approaches has also been explored. While the application of standard KF models achieved good results in predicting short-term worker positions on construction sites [6] and real-time human motion tracking in outdoor environments [20], more advanced models have been proposed to cope with different domain aspects. UKF have been exploited to improve tracking accuracy in noisy environments [13],

while Probabilistic Kalman Filter (PKF) has been used to embed prior trajectory knowledge within a probabilistic graph structure, improving real-time object tracking [21].

Finally, SFM and KF have been jointly considered in complex methods to estimate human movements, while also considering social and environmental interactions [30], [38].

B. Planning-based Models

Planning-based models focus on inferring agents' goals and decision-making strategies through frameworks like Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) and Inverse Reinforcement Learning (IRL). Their strength lies in their interpretability, as they provide insights into the reasoning behind motion trajectories. These models are particularly suited for scenarios where understanding the rationale behind behavior is critical. However, they are often computationally intensive and struggle with scalability. As the number of agents, the size of the environment, or the length of the prediction horizon increases, planning-based approaches typically encounter exponential growth in computational requirements, rendering them less practical for real-time or multi-agent applications.

MDP-based approaches have been successfully exploited to build environment- and intent-aware human motion prediction frameworks, also modeling the joint motion of multiple agents [10], and highlighting the potential of MDP models in mixed-traffic scenarios [11]. The recent definition of Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP)-based online planning method advanced the field by ensuring probabilistic safety in dynamic, multi-agent environments, balancing robustness and real-time performance [47].

In the domain of IRL, several studies have leveraged these kind of methods to infer the latent objectives behind observed motion and predict human goals and actions. Some approaches used first-person video data in indoor environments to demonstrate the value of egocentric perception [8], while others relied on real-world trajectories in outdoor environments to build the models [22], also bypassing the need for explicit action labeling by learning socially compliant navigation policies directly from trajectory data [28].

Beyond traditional planning paradigms, alternative approaches addressed the complexity of human motion prediction by considering the safety-critical perspective [23] and obstacle avoidance in dynamic environments [35]. Promising directions are represented by the joint application of continuous-time Markov Chains (MCs) and Large Language Models (LLMs) to predict human-environment interactions [46], and the adoption of energy optimization-based framework to predict multi-agent trajectories efficiently [48].

C. Pattern-based Models

Pattern-based models, also referred to as data-driven approaches, leverage Machine Learning (ML) techniques to learn motion patterns from data. Architectures such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)—particularly Long Short-Term Memories (LSTMs)—and more recently Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), transformers and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs),

have shown superior performance in structured environments compared to physics- and planning-based models and, in general, do not suffer from the same drawbacks. In fact, pattern-based models excel at identifying complex behavioral patterns and can predict future actions without requiring hand-crafted assumptions [4]. Their primary advantage lies in adaptability and improved accuracy in environments where large volumes of training data are available. Nevertheless, they typically require extensive datasets to be trained and often lack robustness when transferred across domains, which limits their generalizability.

Among the most widely adopted pattern-based approaches are RNNs, particularly LSTM networks, which have been commonly used for pedestrian monitoring in urban traffic environments, also considering human social interactions [7] and pedestrian intent [9], besides human movement. LSTMs have been also combined with attention mechanisms [14], or Graph Attention Networks (GAT) layers [49] to model interactions among multiple pedestrians and capture pedestrian interactions. Beyond urban settings, context-augmented LSTM models have been developed to predict worker trajectories in construction sites [15], [17], [44], or to improve robot navigation in crowded spaces by predicting human motion and adapting navigation policies in response to unexpected behaviors or obstacles [16], [17], [25].

Alternative pattern-based approaches exploited CNNs for predicting human motion in indoor collaborative workspaces [36], or GNNs for multi-modal pedestrian trajectory prediction. Also, the combination of RNNs and GNNs have been explored to predict human trajectories in environments shared with AMRs [4]. Recently, VAEs and Transformers are getting attention and obtained outstanding results in modeling human behavior. In addition to standard VAEs used for pedestrian trajectory prediction [42], Conditional Variational Autoencoders (CVAEs) have also been adopted to predict future pedestrian positions incrementally [41] and to capture both social dynamics and uncertainty in human motion [52], showing interesting performance when applied in multi-agent robotic scenarios [24]. Transformers have been jointly considered with RNN, VAE and MC models for predictions in traffic scenarios [32], stochastic trajectory prediction conditioned on past trajectories and social context in traffic scenarios [33], and to build spatio-temporal Transformer-based architectures [50].

Custom Deep Learning (DL) approaches have also been designed to model human social interactions [29], support pedestrian flow simulating in right-angled corridor environments [54], and to ensure explainability and goal-directed motion [51]. To deal with crowded environment, social-Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional Network (STGCN) has been combined with Reinforcement Learning (RL) to consider crowd-avoidance in robot navigation algorithms. Finally, hybrid models combining SFM, Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), and CVAE have been proposed to generate socially-aware trajectories [43].

D. Research Gaps

Although human motion trajectory prediction has been extensively studied across various domains, relatively few works have focused on its application within indoor industrial environments, particularly those involving the presence of robots, as summarized in Table I. This limited body of research highlights a significant and ongoing gap: the development of models that are not only accurate but also lightweight, privacy-preserving, and suitable for real-time deployment in dynamic industrial settings.

Furthermore, among the existing studies in this area, only a minority consider scenarios involving unfamiliar or previously unexplored environments. Even fewer explicitly focus on human-robot shared workspaces, where a key challenge lies in the dynamic nature of the setting—either the worker, the robot, or both may be in motion. In such contexts, mutual awareness, safety, and adaptability become essential factors for effective collaboration [56]. This under-representation signals an important opportunity for future research to address the unique challenges posed by robotics industrial environments. Specifically, the need for interpretable and robust models that can operate under uncertainty, adapt to changing layouts, and ensure safe coexistence with autonomous systems, such as AMRs.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A modular prototype of a human motion trajectory prediction system is developed to enable flexible and straightforward deployment in diverse real-world scenarios. The system leverages cameras with depth sensors to non-invasively monitor human activity and anticipate future positions. A camera-based setup offers a practical, scalable, and cost-effective solution for real-time human tracking in industrial environments. Unlike GPS or wearable sensors, which may be impractical or intrusive in certain operational contexts, vision-based systems allow for passive monitoring without direct interaction or equipment worn by the subject, along with the possibility of providing contextual information.

A. The System

The proposed system is designed to tackle three main challenges: (i) accurately detect workers in the scene, (ii) estimate their spatial poses (considering both positions and orientations) and (iii) predict their future spatial positions.

The detection phase involves recognizing humans in the scene and computing their poses. This is accomplished using YOLO-pose [57], a state-of-the-art detection model for pose estimation, which is used to process real-time video images from cameras and detect key-points. These key-points, collected from sequential frames, allow the extraction of the following features to build the worker state:

- x_t, y_t : position in $[x, y]$ coordinates.
- \dot{x}_t, \dot{y}_t : linear velocities in x and y .
- θ_{ht}, θ_{bt} : head and body orientation angle.

The $[x, y]$ coordinates of each worker are the result of a depth-based projection that maps $[x, y]$ pixel positions in the frame to a 2D representation.

These features serve as the input for the prediction model and are fed at each time step t . To predict workers motion trajectory, the system employs a KF, which forecasts a worker's future position $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t+w} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ at time $t + w$, based on their state at time t and a customizable time window w . The KF was selected for its computational efficiency, widespread use in human motion prediction, and simplicity of implementation, including the ability to operate without a training phase.

To improve accuracy, the state-of-the-art model which considers only positions and velocities has been extended by incorporating additional features, specifically head and body orientations. Consequently, the human state is represented by a 6-dimensional vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = [x_t \quad y_t \quad \dot{x}_t \quad \dot{y}_t \quad \theta_{ht} \quad \theta_{bt}]^\top$$

Assuming a constant velocity model, the state transition is defined by:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{t-1} + \mathbf{z}_{t-1}$$

with the transition matrix:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

where Δt is the time step between measurements, and \mathbf{z}_{t-1} is zero-mean process noise.

To improve robustness and reduce noise in velocity estimates, a smoothed velocity $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_t$ corresponding to a weighted average is computed over a temporal window of size n :

$$\bar{\mathbf{v}}_t = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_{t-i} \\ \dot{y}_{t-i} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \sum_{i=1}^n k_i = 1$$

here, $\mathbf{v}_{t-i} = [\dot{x}_{t-i}, \dot{y}_{t-i}]^\top$ are past velocity estimates and k_i are linearly decreasing weights prioritizing recent values.

The predicted human position $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t+w}$ after a short time horizon w is estimated using the filtered position and smoothed velocity:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t+w} = \begin{bmatrix} x_t \\ y_t \end{bmatrix} + \alpha \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}}_t \cdot w$$

where x_t, y_t and $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_t$ come from the current KF state estimate \mathbf{x}_t . Additionally, to improve trajectory prediction, the system checks the alignment between the head and body orientations to adjust the predicted motion, under the assumption that if head and body are facing roughly the same direction, then the movement is intentional and consistent. The adjustment is controlled by a factor α , defined as:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \alpha_{\text{aligned}}, & \text{if } |\theta_{ht} - \theta_{bt}| < \delta \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where δ is a threshold defining when head and body orientations are considered aligned, and α_{aligned} is the scaling factor.

Fig. 1: The two validation setups

B. The Setups and the Prototype

The system architecture is designed with modularity and scalability in mind, enabling seamless integration, replacement, or extension of individual components such as detection, tracking, and prediction modules. This flexibility supports rapid experimentation with different models and facilitates deployment across a wide range of scenarios, including both static and dynamic environments.

To validate the system’s functionality and robustness in real-world scenarios, two distinct setups were implemented and are illustrated in Figure 1. The first setup represents a static deployment within a controlled workplace environment, shown in Figure 1a. In this configuration, two Intel RealSense D455 cameras were mounted at fixed positions to provide different Field of Views (FoVs), enabling accurate human detection and tracking across the monitored area. This configuration served as a baseline for evaluating system performance in stable, noise-reduced conditions.

The second setup extends the system to a dynamic use case, where it was integrated onboard an AMR, depicted in Figure 1b. The same type of cameras was mounted at the front and rear of the AMR, allowing a partial perception while navigating the environment, as highlighted in Figure 1c. Despite the motion of the platform, the same detection, tracking and trajectory prediction pipeline was executed in real-time in both configurations, testing the system’s adaptability to changing perspectives and dynamic surroundings.

A system prototype has been realized by integrating the proposed system into the setups. For the experiments, the prototype has been configured by setting $\delta = 30^\circ$ and $\alpha_{\text{aligned}} = 1.2$. More in detail, Figure 2 illustrates the prototype’s interface, which consists of three main components:

- *Real-time video streams*: the system processes live video feeds from both cameras, performing human detection and mapping the workers to specific 3D poses.
- *2D map*: each worker 3D pose is projected onto a 2D

representation and marked as a red dot. The prediction model computes the estimated movements and future positions, which are displayed using green arrows and pink dots, respectively. Instead, head and body orientations are visualized using blue and black arrows. Here, a map pixel corresponds to a centimeter in the reality.

- *Occupancy heatmap*: the system generates a heatmap that discretizes the environment, to visualize the spatial distribution of workers and identify crowded, high-traffic areas. A cell represents 50 cm^2 in the real world.

All experiments were conducted on a high-performance workstation featuring an Intel® Core i9-14900HX processor, 64 GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA RTX 4090 Laptop GPU, which handled the execution of all the models.

IV. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

The system was preliminarily validated through a series of short experiments, each lasting 2 minutes, in which a variable number of workers (ranging from 1 to 3) moved within the monitored workspace. Predictions were evaluated over three different time windows—1, 3, and 5 seconds—using two metrics, both computed by comparing the workers’ predicted positions at time $t + w$ with their actual positions:

- **Accuracy**: based on the number of correct predictions within heatmap cells, introducing spatial tolerance.
- **RMSE**: defined as the Euclidean distance between the predicted and actual workers positions on the 2D map.

In the static scenario, the system was deployed in a fixed location while workers moved freely within the cameras’ FoVs. As shown in Table II, performance declined in multi-worker settings and with longer prediction windows, particularly in presence of occlusions. However, short-term predictions (1s) remained consistent even in multi-worker settings.

To assess the system performance under more variable conditions, similar experiments were performed in the dynamic scenario. In this setup, the system was mounted on an AMR,

Fig. 2: System prototype interface. *Left*: Real-time video streams. *Middle*: 2D map. *Right*: Occupancy heatmap

TABLE II: Validation accuracy and RMSE values within the static scenario

Num workers	t + 1s		t + 3s		t + 5s	
	Acc.	RMSE	Acc.	RMSE	Acc.	RMSE
1	94.9%	19.4	41.2%	92.5	24.9%	110.1
2	88.8%	31.3	27.2%	101.9	19.4%	131.2
3	83.0%	54.1	26.9%	127.0	16.0%	140.1

with cameras positioned to monitor the front and rear views during navigation through a shared workspace. The AMR followed a predefined route, continuously moving, changing direction and rotating to reach successive destinations. Table III summarizes the results.

TABLE III: Validation accuracy and RMSE values within the dynamic scenario (onboard the AMR)

Num workers	t + 1s		t + 3s		t + 5s	
	Acc.	RMSE	Acc.	RMSE	Acc.	RMSE
1	69.1%	33.0	25.5%	113.8	18.5%	225.4
2	57.6%	61.5	22.2%	148.0	14.1%	240.5
3	53.8%	154.4	15.6%	203.4	11.7%	296.5

While short-term predictions (1s) remained partially reliable even under dynamic conditions, the system showed notable limitations, in particular for longer prediction horizons and in multi-worker scenarios, similarly to the static setup. Although human motion trajectory prediction systems can support longer-term path planning, short-term predictions are still crucial, as they contribute significantly to reducing the risk of collisions.

One key challenge in both scenarios was the handling of occlusions and overlappings: without identity-preserving mechanisms, the system struggled to maintain coherent tracking when workers occluded each other or were partially hidden behind obstacles. This is an inherent limitation of the system, which prioritizes the anonymity of workers. Additionally, in the dynamic setup, the AMR’s continuous movements introduced perspective shifts and perception noise, which negatively impacted prediction performance. Environmental

constraints in this scenario further exacerbated these issues. In particular, narrow corridors and confined spaces limited the cameras’ FoV, hindering accurate human detection and localization—especially during AMR rotations or when workers moved very close to its sides, often falling outside the effective viewing range. Predictions were significantly more accurate when workers were fully visible and located within the optimal sensing range (1 to 6 meters) of the system. Furthermore, a small number of false positives were observed in human detection, likely caused by reflective surfaces, machinery, or intrinsic variability of the industrial environment.

Despite these challenges, the prediction module demonstrated stable performance across different motion conditions, maintaining comparable accuracy whether the AMR, the workers, or both were in motion. This robustness confirms the system’s applicability for short-term, reactive planning in dynamic, human-robot shared environments. Notably, the system exhibited a consistent ability to adjust to sudden changes in motion trajectories, suggesting potential for integration with higher-level planning frameworks. However, these findings also underscore the need for enhanced occlusions handling, improved contextual awareness, robust human tracking and future position prediction strategies.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented an approach to human motion trajectory prediction in industrial environments, based on worker detection, pose estimation and KF-based future position prediction. The system was validated in both static and dynamic scenarios, with the latter involving onboard deployment on an AMR navigating a shared workspace.

While the KF offers efficient, interpretable and low-latency predictions, it presents several limitations that impact its robustness in real-world applications. Moreover, the lack of contextual awareness—such as the presence of obstacles or workstation constraints—can lead to unrealistic forecasts. Orientation estimation was also found to be unreliable in some cases, and privacy-preserving design choices prevented identity-based tracking, reducing consistency across time and complicating multi-worker scenarios. Results indicated that short-term predictions (1s) were consistently reliable

across both scenarios, whereas performance declined with longer prediction windows and in multi-worker settings. This degradation was mainly due to occlusions and limited FoV, with the dynamic scenario further affected by noise introduced by the AMR's movement.

Despite the limitations above, this work establishes a solid foundation for extensions. Future developments could benefit from integrating identity-tracking algorithms, multi-sensor fusion, or predictive modeling of occluded agents to further improve performance in densely populated or geometrically constrained industrial settings. Next steps will also focus on integrating environmental context and supporting more robust human motion trajectory prediction models, including pattern-based approaches such as LSTMs, GNNs, and their combinations. The ultimate goal is to deploy a reliable and robust prediction system in dynamic shared workspaces. This approach is crucial to enable proactive path planning and adaptive safety mechanisms, that enhance both efficiency and HRC, by offering real-time adaptation, coordination, and collision prevention.

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